

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND FITNESS SMARTPHONE APPS USE IN HEALTHY PEOPLE: AN EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS WITHIN THE DARE PROJECT

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"what's new"

PNRR Project DARE (DigitAl lifelong pRevEntion), aimed at developing digital tools to monitor lifestyles (PA) and implementing interventions for primary prevention:
→ select or develop new apps incorporating multiple sensors for the collection of multiple data in wide populations.

"what's interesting"

- all the retrieved apps effective in increasing PA/fitness
- no apps targeted to children
- missing apps tested in various wide world areas
- few apps with multiple sensors
- less than half apps validated
- behavior change techniques not reported in more than half studies

